

Biological importance of phytochemical constituents isolated from genus *Eugenia*[†]

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Abstract : *Eugenia* (Myrtaceae) is the largest genus comprising over 1000 species with centers of concentration in tropical and sub-tropical America and tropical Asia, with a few species occurring in Australia and Africa. The compounds generally associated with this genus are flavonoids and triterpenoids, although chalcones and tannins are also present. Among the flavonoids, such as glycosides or aglycone, there is a predominance of polyhydroxylated flavanols. The majority of compounds isolated from these species are pentacyclic triterpenes with a lupane or oleanane skeleton. These compounds exhibit numerous pharmacological activities including analgesic, antipyretic, antifungal, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antioxidant activity. We have systematically reviewed *Eugenia* genus as it may be helpful to pharmaceutical and food industry as well as biologists, pharmacologists and phytochemists.

Keywords : Genus *Eugenia*, Myrtaceae, triterpenoids, tannins, flavonoids, biological activities.

Introduction

The pan-tropic genus *Eugenia* belongs to Myrtaceae. This is a large and well defined family, with about 140 genera and about 4000 species. The genus *Eugenia* comprises over 1000 species with centers of concentration in tropical and sub-tropical America and tropical Asia, with a few species occurring in Australia and Africa. It is the largest genus in the Myrtaceae family in tropical America¹. A study suggested that 350 out of 1000 species of this genus are native from Brazil². This genus of evergreen trees or shrubs produces fleshy spherical fruits which are by and large edible³.

Eugenia jambolana (Black Plum; known in India as Jaman), *Eugenia uniflora* (Surinam cherry; known in Brazil as pitanga) and *Eugenia edulis* (known in Brazil as jaboticaba) produce widely consumed, tasty and medicinally used fruits. The sweet and sour ripe fruits of these species are used to prepare health drinks, squashes, juices, jellies, vinegar and wine^{4,5}. The orange, red, purple, and black (dark purple) edible fruits produced by the species of *Eugenia* suggested that they are the rich source of antioxidant phytochemicals, especially, anthocyanins. The

wine colored new shoot of a large number of *Eugenia* species suggested that their leaves are also the rich source of anthocyanins^{4,6}. Extensive ethnobotanical and ethnomedical uses of fruits, seeds, leaves and bark of this genus are reported in literature.

Syrup or vinegar prepared from ripe fruits of *E. jambolana* is used in spleen enlargement and chronic diarrhea^{7,8}. The seeds are used to control sugar in urine and allay the unquenchable thirst of diabetes⁸.

Fruits of *E. uniflora* are eaten for intestinal troubles⁹ and leaves as well as fruits are also used for their astringent qualities, and to treat high blood pressure and lower cholesterol^{10,11}. *Syzygium jambos* fruit is used as a tonic for the brain and for liver problems^{12,13}. The leaves are used as an anesthetic, anti-inflammatory, and astringent, for apoplexy, asthma, bronchitis, cough, diabetes, dysentery, influenza, and rheumatism⁹. The fruits of *E. edulis* are popular edible in Brazil, much like grapes in the United States⁶. In addition, decoctions of the sun-dried skins fruit have been used for a variety of inflammatory conditions, including hemoptysis, asthma, diarrhea, and tonsillitis.

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Phytoconstituents isolated from genus <i>Eugenia</i> and their pharmacological activities					
Compd. no.	Compd. name	Isolated part	Species	Activities	Refs.
Triterpenoids					
1	2 α ,3 β -Dihydroxylup-12-en-28-oic acid	Stem bark	<i>E. grandis</i>		31
2	3 β -Hydroxylup-12-en-28-oic acid	Stem bark	<i>E. grandis</i>		31
3	Betulinic acid	Stem bark, leaves	<i>E. grandis</i> , <i>E. jambolana</i> , <i>E. sandwicensis</i>		31–34
4	Oleanolic acid	Stem bark, leaves, flowers	<i>E. grandis</i> , <i>E. jambolana</i> , <i>E. javanica</i>		31, 32, 35–37
5	Friedlin	Stem bark	<i>E. grandis</i>		31, 38, 39
6	3 β -Fridelinol	Stem bark	<i>E. grandis</i>		31, 40, 41
7	Crategolic (Maslinic acid) acid	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>		34
8	3 β - <i>cis-p</i> -Coumaroyloxy-2 α ,23-dihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
9	3 β - <i>trans-p</i> -Coumaroyloxy-2 α ,23-dihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
10	23- <i>trans-p</i> -Coumaroyloxy-2 β ,3 α -dihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
11	Alphitolic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
12	Arjunolic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
13	3-Epi betulinic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
14	2 α ,3 α -Dihydroxylup-20(29)-en-28-oic acid	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
15	Hederagenin	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>		42
Phloroglucinol-monoterpenoids					
16	Eugenial A	Fruits	<i>E. multiflora</i>	Gastroprotective	43
17	Eugenial B	Fruits	<i>E. multiflora</i>	Gastroprotective	43
Sesquiterpenoids					
18	β -Caryophyllene	Whole plant	<i>E. caryophyllata</i> , <i>E. uniflora</i>	Antimicrobial, Anticarcinogenic, Anti-inflammatory	44–47
19	β -Caryophyllene oxide	Whole plant	<i>E. caryophyllata</i>		44
20	α -Humulene	Whole plant	<i>E. caryophyllata</i>	Anticarcinogenic, Anti-inflammatory	44, 46, 47
21	α -Humulene epoxide	Whole plant	<i>E. caryophyllata</i>	Anticarcinogenic	44
22	Atractylone	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antinoceptive, Hypothermic	48
23	3-Furanoeudesmene	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antinoceptive, Hypothermic	48
24	Curzerene	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antimicrobial	45

Gupta *et al.* : Biological importance of phytochemical constituents isolated from genus *Eugenia*

Contd.

25	Seline-1,3,7-trien-8-one oxide	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antimicrobial	45
26	Seline-1,3,7-trien-8-one	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antifungal	45
27	Germacrene A	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antifungal	45
28	Germacrene B	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antifungal	45
29	Germacrene D	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	Antifungal	45
Phenylpropanoids					
30	Eugenol	Whole plant	<i>E. caryophyllata</i>	Anti-carcinogenic	44
Flavonoids					
31	Gossypetin-3,8-dimethyl ether-5- <i>O</i> - β -glucoside	Leaves	<i>E. edulis</i>		49
32	Gossypetin-3,5-dimethyl ether	Leaves	<i>E. edulis</i>		49
33	Myricetin-3,5,3'-trimethyl ether	Leaves	<i>E. edulis</i>		49
34	Mearnsetin 3- <i>O</i> -(4''- <i>O</i> -acetyl)- α -L-rhamnopyranoside (Myricetin 4'-methyl ether)	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>		50
35	Myricetrin 4''- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2''- <i>O</i> -gallate	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>		50
36	Myricetin 3- <i>O</i> -(4''- <i>O</i> -acetyl)- α -L-rhamnopyranoside i.e. (Myricetrin 4''- <i>O</i> -acetate)	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>		50
37	Myricetin 4'-methyl ether-3- <i>O</i> - α -L-rhamnopyranoside	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>		50
38	Myricitrin	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i> , <i>E. uniflora</i> , <i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	50, 51
39	Quercetin	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Tyrosinase inhibitory	49-53
40	Myricetin	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i> , <i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	50, 51
41	Iso-quercitrin	Leaves	<i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	51
42	Rutin	Leaves	<i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	51
43	Kaempferol	Seeds, stems and leaves	<i>E. edulis</i>		49, 50, 52
Galloyl Arbituns					
44	Hyemaloside A	Green tree (Menus root)	<i>E. hymalis</i>	Anti HIV	54
45	Hyemaloside B	Green tree (Menus root)	<i>E. hymalis</i>	Anti HIV	54
46	Hyemaloside C	Green tree (Menus root)	<i>E. hymalis</i>	Anti HIV	54

47	2,6-Di- <i>O</i> -galloylarbttin	Green tree (Menus root)	<i>E. hymalis</i>		54
Tannins					
(I) Hydrolyzable tannins :					
48	Castalagin	Leaves	<i>E. grandis</i>		55
49	Vascalagin	Leaves	<i>E. grandis</i>		55
50	Eugeniflorin D ₁	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	EBV DNA polymerase	56, 57
51	Eugeniflorin D ₂	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	EBV DNA polymerase	56, 57
52	Oenothein B	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	EBV DNA polymerase, antitumour	56, 57
(II) Ellagetannin :					
53	1- <i>O</i> -Galloyl castalagin	Leaves	<i>E. grandis</i> , <i>E. jabolana</i>	Antiproliferative	55, 58
54	Casuarinin	Leaves	<i>E. jabolana</i>	Antiproliferative	58, 59
55	Oenohein C	Seeds	<i>E. jabolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory	59, 60
56	Iso-oenothein C	Fruit seeds	<i>E. jabolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory	60
57	Corusiin B	Seeds	<i>E. jabolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory	60
58	Nilocitin	Leaves	<i>E. jabolana</i>		50
(III) Gallotannins :					
59	Gallocatechin	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	EBV DNA polymerase	56, 57
60	Catechin	Leaves	<i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	51
61	Epi-catechin	Leaves	<i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	51
62	Jamutannin A	Fruit seeds	<i>E. jabolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory	60
63	Jamutannin B	Fruit seeds	<i>E. jabolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory	60
Anthocyanins					
64	Delphinidin-3- <i>O</i> - β - glucopyranoside	Fruit	<i>E. umbelliflora</i>	Anticancer	61
65	Cyanidin-3- <i>O</i> - β - glucopyranoside	Fruit	<i>E. umbelliflora</i>	Anticancer	61
66	Petunidin-3- <i>O</i> - β - glucopyranoside	Fruit	<i>E. umbelliflora</i>	Anticancer	61
67	Pelargonidin-3- <i>O</i> - β - glucopyranoside	Fruit	<i>E. umbelliflora</i>	Anticancer	61
68	Peonidin-3- <i>O</i> - β - glucopyranoside	Fruit	<i>E. umbelliflora</i>	Anticancer	61
69	Malvidin-3- <i>O</i> - β - glucopyranoside	Fruit	<i>E. umbelliflora</i>	Anticancer	61

Sterols				
70	Stigmasterol	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
71	β -Sitosterol	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	31, 34
Phenolics				
72	Valonic acid dilactone	Seeds	<i>E. jambolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory 62
73	Phyllanthusiin E	Seeds	<i>E. jambolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory 63
74	Brevifolin carboxylic acid	Seeds	<i>E. jambolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory 64
75	Swertisin	Seeds	<i>E. jambolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory 65
76	Syringaldehyde	Stems	<i>E. sandwicensis</i>	42
Polyphenolics				
77	Gallic acid	Seeds, stems and leaves	<i>E. edulis</i> , <i>E. uniflora</i> , <i>E. jambolana</i> , <i>E. dysenteria</i> , <i>E. sandwicensis</i>	Antioxidative, Tyrosinase inhibitory, α -Glucosodase inhibitory 49–51, 66
78	Protocatechuic acid (3,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid)	Seeds, stems and leaves	<i>E. edulis</i> , <i>E. jambolana</i>	49
79	Methyl gallate	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	50
80	Ellagic acid	Seeds and leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	α -Glucosodase inhibitory 50, 67
81	3- <i>O</i> -Methyl ellagic acid	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	50
82	Chlorogenic acid	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	50
83	1,2,6-Tri- <i>O</i> -galloyl- β -D-glucose	Roots	<i>E. hyemalica</i>	54, 57
84	1,2,4,6-Tetra- <i>O</i> -galloyl- β -D-glucose	Leaves	<i>E. uniflora</i>	57
85	Kojic acid	Leaves	<i>E. dysenteria</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory 51
Aliphatic alcohols				
86	<i>n</i> -Octacosanol	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
87	<i>n</i> -Triaccontanol	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
88	<i>n</i> -Dotriacontanol	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
<i>n</i>-Alkanes (<i>n</i>-paraffins)				
89	<i>n</i> -Heptacosane	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
90	<i>n</i> -Nonacosane	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
91	<i>n</i> -Triaccontane	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
92	<i>n</i> -Hentriacontane acids	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
Acids				
93	Oxalic acid	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
94	Citric acid	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
Amino acids				
95	Glycine	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
96	Alanine	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
97	Tyrosine	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34
98	Leucine	Leaves	<i>E. jambolana</i>	34

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8 : $R_1 = \text{cis-}p\text{-Coumaroyloxy}$, $R_2 = \text{OH}$
 9 : $R_1 = \text{trans-}p\text{-Coumaroyloxy}$, $R_2 = \text{OH}$
 10 : $R_1 = \text{OH}$, $R_2 = \text{trans-}p\text{-Coumaroyloxy}$

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16 : R = CH₂CH₂CH₃

17 : R = CH₂CH₂CH₃

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31 : $R_1 = \text{Glc}, R_2 = \text{OCH}_3, R_3 = \text{H}$

32 : $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{OH}, R_3 = \text{H}$

33 : $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$

34 : $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = -\text{COCH}_3$

35 : $R_1 = \text{H}, R_3 = -\text{COCH}_3$

36 : $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = -\text{COCH}_3$

37 : $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$

38 : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$

39 : $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{H}$

40 : $R_1 = \text{OH}, R_2 = \text{H}$

41 : $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Glucosyl}$

42 : $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Rutinosyl}$

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44 : $R_1, R_2, R_3 = \text{G}$

45 : $R_1 = \text{G}, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{X}$

46 : $R_1, R_2 = G$

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48 : $R_1 = OH, R_2 = H$

49 : $R_1 = H, R_2 = OH$

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58 : $R_1-R_2 = (S)\text{-HHDP}$, $R_3 = R_4 = H$

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- 64 : $R_1 = \text{OH}, R_2 = \text{OH}$
 65 : $R_1 = \text{OH}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 66 : $R_1 = \text{OCH}_3, R_2 = \text{OH}$
 67 : $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 68 : $R_1 = \text{OCH}_3, R_2 = \text{H}$
 69 : $R_1 = \text{OCH}_3, R_2 = \text{OCH}_3$

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Genus *Eugenia* shows a wide array of biological activities, like analgesic, antipyretic^{14,15}, antifungal¹⁶, antimicrobial¹⁷, antioxidant¹⁸, antidiabetic¹⁹, anti-inflammatory²⁰, hepatoprotective²¹, and antioxidant activity^{22,23}. The compounds generally associated with this genus are flavonoids and triterpenoids, although chalcones²⁴ and tannins²⁵ are also present. Among the flavonoids, such as glycosides or aglycone, there is a predominance of polyhydroxylated flavanols²⁶. The majority of compounds isolated from these species²⁷ are pentacyclic triterpenes with a lupane or oleanane skeleton.

Leaf extracts of 17 Neotropical and Paleotropical *Eugenia* species contained myricetin, quercetin, kaempferol²⁸, ellagic acid, methylellagic acid, procyanidin, and prodelpinidin have been found in many species of *Eugenia*^{29,30}.

In view of the immense pharmacological, biological and nutraceutical importance of the genus *Eugenia* we have systematically reviewed this genus as it may be helpful to pharmaceutical and food industry as well as biologists, pharmacologists and phytochemists.

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References

- R. Govaerts, M. Sobral, P. Ashton, F. Barrie, B. K. Holst, L. R. Landrum, K. Matsumoto, F. F. Mazine, E. N. Lughadha, C. Proença, L. H. Soares-Silva, P. G. Wilson and E. Lucas, "World Checklist of Myrtaceae", Royal Botanic Garden, Kew, 2008.
- L. R. Landrum and M. L. Kawasaki, *Brittonia.*, 1997, **49**, 508.
- M. Auricchio and E. M. Bacchi, *Rev. Inst. Adolfo Lutz*, 2003, **62**, 55.
- S. Facciola, *Cornucopia II*. Vista, CA : Kampong Publications, 1998, p. 157.
- M. S. Baligaa, H. P. Bhatd, B. R. V. Baligab, R. Wilsonc and P. L. Palatyb, *Phytochemistry*, 2011, **44**, 1776.
- W. Popenoe, "Manual of Tropical and Subtropical Fruits", Hafner Press, New York, 1920, p. 272.
- "Bhavaprakash Nighantu", eds. G. S. Pandey and C. Bharti, Academy, 1998, p. 570.
- "Indian Materia Medica", eds. A. K. Nadkarni, Popular Prakashan, 1976, p. 516.
- D. Rivera and C. Obón, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 1995, **46**, 73.
- A. L. Bandoni, M. E. Mendiondo, R. V. D. Rondina and J. D. Coussio, *Lloydia*, 1972, **35**, 69.
- E. Ferro, A. Schinini, M. Maldonado, J. Rosner and G. S. Hirschman, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 1988, **24**, 321.
- N. C. Winterville and J. Morton, *J. Fruits of Warm Climates*, 1987, 386.
- K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", International Book Distributors, Dehradun, 1988, Vol. **II**, p.1038.
- S. Karla, E. Carretero and A. Villar, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 1994, **43**, 9.
- S. Karla, S. Monica, C. Emilia and V. Angel, *Phytochemistry*, 1994, **37**, 255.
- M. M. Rahhal, *Alexandria Sci. Exch.*, 1997, **18**, 225.
- A. Dzamic, M. Sokovic, M. S. Ristic, S. Grijic-Jovanovic, J. Vukojevic and P. D. Marin, *Chem. Nat. Comp.*, 2009, **45**, 269; K. E. Machado, V. Cechinel Filho, R. Tessarolo, C. Mallmann, C. Meyre-Silva and A. Bella Cruz, *Pharm. Biol.*, 2005, **43**, 636.
- I. Gülçin, G. S. S. Beydemir, M. Elmasta and Ö. Küfrevioglu, *Food Chem.*, 2004, **87**, 393; K. Ravi, B. Ramachandran and S. Subramanian, *Life Sci.*, 2004, **75**, 2717; M. D. A. Magina, A. Gilioli, H. H. Moresco, G. Colla, M. G. Pizzolatti and I. M. C. Brighente, *Latin Am. J. Pharm.*, 2010, **29**, 376.
- S. B. Sharma, A. Nasir, K. M. Prabhu and P. S. Murthy, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2006, **104**, 367; B. Sharma, G. Viswanath, R. Salunke and P. Roy, *Food Chem.*, 2008, **110**, 697; V. Vikrant, J. K. Grover, N. Tandon, S. S. Rathi and N. Gupta, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2001, **76**, 139.
- M. D. A. Magina, E. F. Pietrovski, F. Gomig, D. B. Falkenberg, D. A. Cabrini, M. F. Otuki, M. G. Pizzolatti and I. M. C. Brighente, *Braz. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2009, **45**, 171; D. Ávila-Penã, N. Penã, L. Quintero and H. Suárez-Roca, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2007, **112**, 380.
- S. Rasheed, M. Tahir, W. Sami and B. Munir, *J. Ayub. Med. Coll. Abbottabad.*, 2009, **21**.
- E. de Oliveira Figueirôa, L. C. N. da Silva, C. M. L. de Melo, J. K. de Andrade Lemoine Neves, N. H. da Silva, V. R. A. Pereira and M. T. dos Santos Correia, *The Scientific World Journal*, 2013, **2013**, Article ID 125027.
- S. A. Sheikh, M. Shahnawaz, S. M. Nizamani, M. I. Bhangar and E. Ahmed, *J. Pharm. Nutr. Sci.*, 2011, **1**, 41.
- M. R. Simirgiotis, S. Adachi, S. To, H. Yang, K. A. Reynertson, M. J. Basile, R. R. Gil, I. B. Weinstein and E. J. Kennelly, *Food Chem.*, 2008, **107**, 813.
- L. L. Yang, C. Y. Lee and K. Y. Yen, *Cancer Lett.*, 2000, **157**, 65.

Gupta *et al.* : Biological importance of phytochemical constituents isolated from genus *Eugenia*

26. S. A. M. Hussein, A. N. M. Hashem, M. A. Selien, U. Lindequist and M. A. M. Nawwar, *Phytochemistry*, 2003, **64**, 883.
27. J. Q. Gu, E. J. Park, L. Luyengi, M. E. Hawthorne, R. G. Mehta, N. R. Farnsworth, J. M. Pezzuto and A. D. Kinghorn, *Phytochemistry*, 2001, **58**, 121.
28. N. W. Haron, D. M. Moore and J. B. Harborne, *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology*, 1992, **20**, 226.
29. A. G. R. Nair, S. Krishnan, C. Ravikrishna and K. P. Madhusudanan, *Fitoterapia*, 1999, **70**, 148.
30. R. Hegnauer, "Chemotaxonomie der Pflanzen", Birkhäuser Verlag, Berlin, 1990, **9**, p. 119.
31. K. P. Manoharan, F. J. Song, T. K. H. Benny and D. Yang, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 2007, **45**, 279.
32. A. Ikudta and H. Itokawa, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 2813.
33. C. Peng, G. Bodenhausen, S. Qiu, H. H. S. Fong, N. R. Farnsworth, S. Yuan and C. Zheng, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1998, **36**, 267.
34. G. S. Gupta and D. P. Sharma, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, **13**, 2013.
35. S. B. Mahato and A. P. Kundu, *Phytochemistry*, 1994, **41**, 883.
36. K. S. Adesina and J. Reisch, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 3003.
37. W. Seebacher, N. Simic, R. Weis, R. Saf and O. Kunert, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 2003, **41**, 636.
38. J. Klass, W. F. Tinto, S. McLean and W. F. Reynolds, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1992, **55**, 1626.
39. K. S. E. Deeb, A. Rwaidda, J. S. M. Ai-Haidari and A. Abdel-Monem, *Saudi Pharm. J.*, 2003, **11**, 184.
40. J. K. Kundu, *Fitoterapia*, 2000, **71**, 574.
41. C. Betancor, R. Freire, A. G. Gonzalez, J. A. Salazar, C. Pascard and T. Prange, *Phytochemistry*, 1980, **19**, 1989.
42. Jian-Qiao Gu, E. J. Park, L. Luyengi, M. E. Hawthorne, R. G. Mehta, N. R. Farnsworth, J. M. Pezzuto and A. D. Kinghorn, *Phytochemistry*, 2001, **58**, 121.
43. L. G. Faqueti, C. M. Petry, C. Meyre-Silva, K. E. Machado, A. B. Cruz, P. A. Garcia, V. Cechinel-Filho, A. S. Feliciano and F. D. Monache, *Nat. Prod. Res.*, 2013, **27**, 28.
44. G.-Q. Zheng, P. M. Kenney and L. K. T. Lam, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1992, **55**, 999.
45. F. N. Victoria, E. J. Lenardão, L. Savegnago, G. Perin, R. G. Jacob, D. Alves, W. Padilha da Silva, A. de S. da Motta and P. da Silva Nascente, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 2012, **50**, 2668.
46. K. Cal, *Planta Med.*, 2006, **3**, 1.
47. E. S. Fernandes, G. F. Passos, R. Medeiros, F. M. Cunha, J. Ferreira, M. M. Campos, L. F. Pianowski and J. B. Calixto, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 2007, **569**, 228.
48. A. C. L. Amorim, C. K. F. Lima, A. M. C. Hovell, A. L. P. Miranda and C. M. Rezende, *Phytomedicine*, 2009, **16**, 923.
49. S. A. M. Husseina, A. N. M. Hashema, M. A. Seliemb, U. Lindequist and M. A. M. Nawwara, *Phytochemistry*, 2003, **64**, 883.
50. I. I. Mahmoud, M. S. A. Marzouk, F. A. Moharram, M. R. El-Gindi and A. M. K. Hassan, *Phytochemistry*, 2001, **58**, 1239.
51. P. M. Souza, S. T. Elias, L. A. Simeoni, J. E. de Paula, S. M. Gomes, E. N. S. Guerra, Y. M. Fonseca, E. C. Silva, D. Silveira and P. O. Magalhaes, *www.plosone.org.*, 2012, **7**, 1.
52. M. A. M. Nawwar, A. M. A. Souleman, J. Buddrus and M. Linscheid, *Phytochemistry*, 1984b, **23**, 2347.
53. K. Slowing, M. Söllhuber, E. Carretero and A. Villar, *Phytochemistry*, 1994, **37**, 255.
54. H. R. Bokesch, A. Wamiru, S. F. J. Le Grice, J. A. Beutler, T. C. McKee and J. B. McMahon, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2008, **71**, 1634.
55. G. I. Nonaka, K. Ishimaru, M. Watanabe, I. Nishioka, T. Yamauchi and A. S. C. Wan, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1987, **35**, 217.
56. M. H. Lee, S. Nishimoto, L. L. Yang, K. Y. Yen, T. Hatano, T. Yoshida and T. Okuda, *Phytochemistry*, 1997, **44**, 1343.
57. M. H. Lee, J. F. Chiou, K. Y. Yen and L. L. Yang, *Cancer Lett.*, 2000, **154**, 131.
58. L. L. Yang, C. Y. Lee and K. Y. Yen, *Cancer Lett.*, 2000, **157**, 65.
59. T. Hatano, N. Ogawa, R. Kira, T. Yasuhara and T. Okuda, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1989, **37**, 2083.
60. R. Omar, L. Li, T. Yuan and N. P. Seeram, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2012, **75**, 1505.
61. E. M. Kuskoski, J. M. Vega, J. J. Rios, R. Fett, A. Troncoso and A. G. Asuero, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2003, **51**, 5450.
62. H. H. Barakata, S. A. M. Hussein, M. S. Marzouka, I. Merfort, M. Linscheid and M. A. M. Nawwar, *Phytochemistry*, 1997, **46**, 935.
63. T. Yoshida, H. Itoh, S. Matsunaga, R. Tanaka and T. Okuda, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1992, **40**, 53.
64. R. Saijo, G. Nonaka and I. Nishioka, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1989, **37**, 2624.
65. O. BJOROY, S. RAYYAN, T. FOSSEN, K. KALBERG and O. M. ANDERSEN, *Phytochemistry*, 2009, **70**, 278.
66. L. Li and N. P. Seeram, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2010, **58**, 11673.
67. X. Li, H. N. Elsohly, C. D. Hufford and A. M. Clark, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1999, **37**, 856.

